

From Inception to Destruction of Nalanda University Library: A Study Through Historical Prospective

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Abstract: *Nalanda, an ancient center of higher learning in Bihar, India, thrived from 427 CE to 1197 CE, becoming a renowned Buddhist monastic university. Established by the Gupta emperors in the 5th century, it flourished for nearly seven centuries, offering studies in subjects such as fine arts, medicine, mathematics, astronomy, politics, and war, besides Buddhist scriptures. The heart of Nalanda's intellectual prowess was its vast library, known as Dharmaganja, which housed hundreds of thousands of manuscripts spread across three multi-story buildings.*

The collection of the Nalanda library was vast, with an extensive array of Buddhist scriptures, philosophical treatises, scientific and technical texts, historical documents, and literary works. Scholars and students from various parts of Asia were drawn to Nalanda due to the richness of its library, which served as a critical repository of knowledge and academic rigor.

Despite its global prominence, Nalanda was destroyed several times, with the final destruction occurring around 1193 CE by the Turkish invader Bakhtiyar Khilji. This attack led to the burning of its immense collection, reportedly taking months for the library to be completely engulfed in flames. The loss of Nalanda marked a profound setback in Buddhist learning and scholarship in India.

Efforts to revive the legacy of Nalanda began in the 19th century through archaeological excavations, leading to the re-establishment of Nalanda University in 2014 as a modern institution. Although much of the ancient knowledge was lost, Nalanda's significance as a historical and academic symbol continues to influence educational endeavours today.

Keywords: Nalanda University, Ancient libraries, Buddhist learning, Dharmaganja, Bakhtiyar Khilji, Library destruction, Buddhist manuscripts, Nalanda excavations

Introduction

Nalanda is an ancient center of higher learning in Bihar, India from 427 to 1197. Nalanda was founded by the Gupta emperors in the early 5th century and then expanded over the next 7 centuries. It was

Founded in 427 in northeastern India, not far from what is today the southern border of Nepal, it survived until 1197. It was devoted to Buddhist studies, but it also trained students in fine arts, medicine, mathematics, astronomy, politics and the art of war. The center had eight separate compounds, 10 temples, meditation halls, classrooms, lakes and parks. It had a nine-story library where monks meticulously copied books and documents so that individual scholars could have their own collections.

Archeological excavations in the site during 1920-1921 discovered a thick layer of ashes on the uppermost strata, across many buildings separated by some distance; this suggests that Nalanda was subject to a catastrophic fire. Traditionally, this is held to be an arson, blamed upon the troops of Muhammad Bakhtiyar Khilji who had plundered the region c. 1200 CE, and cited to be the leading cause of Nalanda's demise.

Research Question:

What is the general history of the Nalanda library?

What was the collections of the library?

What is the reason for which the library is lost?

Objective Of the Study:

Mapping the history of the Nalanda library and how the library lost or destroyed.

To know period wise development and use of library collection in Nalanda Library.

Scope and Limitation:

The scope of this study is that the researcher only study about the Destruction Nalanda library which is burnt in the past period. In this study, the researcher covers the origin, development, collection, use, and destruction of the library. The limitation of this study is that it only collects data from primary, secondary, and web and document surveys; the researcher did not personally visit that place. The researcher collects the data that is available in documents or on authentic websites.

Methodology:

Since the present study is purely on the Destruction Nalanda library in the past period. In order to investigate the problem of the proposed research and to achieve our objectives stated earlier, it has been intended to adopt a method like document research. Document research will be applied for making related and relevant literature reviews, secondary data analyses, and archives studies, which are the most important parts of the research. The data was also collected from different websites, like Google Scholar, Shodhganga, ResearchGate, Wikipedia, and different journal sites.

Literature Rivew:

Vishnu Kumar Gupta (2018) conducted a study entitled "Burning Libraries: A Review Through the Lens of History". This study describes whether the libraries were burned accidentally or purposefully. In this study, the researcher describes the library's origin, its establishment, its collection, and its destruction. In this study, the researcher describes the Alexandria Library, the Nalanda University Library, Washington, DC, and some other libraries. The researcher also describes disaster management in modern libraries, causes of fire by human action, and rules and standards for fire protection.

Bimal Kumar Datta (2016) conducted a study entitled "Libraries and Librarianship in Ancient and Mediaeval India from the Earliest Time to C. 1850". In this study, the researcher describes the development of libraries in India in the ancient and mediaeval periods in different regions. The researcher also describes the writing materials, the introduction of paper, the binding of manuscripts, library administration, and the introduction of printing in India.

Pintu Kumar (2011) conducted a study entitled "The Ancient Nalanda Mahavihara: The Beginning of Institutional Education". In this study, the researcher describes that the Nalanda University library is unique for its rich collection of Buddhist texts at that time, and the library is also a storehouse of priceless manuscripts.

Library of Nalanda University

Nalanda is an ancient center of higher learning in Bihar, India from 427 to 1197. Nalanda was established in the 5th century AD in Bihar, India. Founded in 427 in northeastern India, not far from what is today the southern border of Nepal, it survived until 1197. It was devoted to Buddhist studies, but it also trained students in fine arts, medicine, mathematics, astronomy, politics and the art of war. The center had eight separate compounds, 10 temples, meditation halls, classrooms, lakes and parks.

According to the Chinese monk Yijing Nalanda had a nine-story library named Dharmaganja meaning (at the market of faith) which comprised three large multi-storeyed buildings, the Ratnasagara (Ocean of Jewels), the Ratnodadhi (Sea of Jewels), and the Ratnaranjaka (Jewel-adorned). Ratnodadhi was nine storeys high and housed the most sacred manuscripts including the Prajnyaparamita Sutra and the Guhyasamaja. where monks meticulously copied books and documents so that individual scholars could have their own collections.

Numerous texts make this clear that Yijing carried back with him after his 10-year residence at Nalanda, that the Mahavihara must have featured a well-equipped library. When he returned to China in 695, he had with him 400 Sanskrit texts and 300 grains of Buddha relics which were subsequently translated in China. Also, in the Traditional Tibetan sources mention the existence of a great library at Nalanda. Nalanda University Library holds a significant place in the history of academia and knowledge dissemination. it flourished as a center of learning for several centuries, attracting scholars and students from all over Asia.

The library at Nalanda University was renowned for its vast collection of manuscripts and texts covering various fields of knowledge, including Buddhism, mathematics, astronomy, medicine, logic, and philosophy. It played a crucial role in the preservation and transmission of knowledge during ancient times.

The architecture of the library was grand, reflecting the scholarly and intellectual pursuits of the time. It is said to have been a nine-story building, with meticulously organized shelves and reading rooms. The library was a symbol of the intellectual richness and scholarly pursuits that characterized Nalanda University.

(Picture of Nalanda University after Excavations)

Library collection

The exact number of volumes in the Nalanda library is not known, but it is estimated to have been in the hundreds of thousands. The library collection at Nalanda University during its prime was renowned for its vast and diverse range of manuscripts and texts. Scholars and students from different parts of Asia were drawn to Nalanda precisely because of the richness of its library. The collection covered a wide array of subjects, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of the university's curriculum and the intellectual pursuits of the time.

Buddhist Texts: As a center of Buddhist learning, Nalanda's library housed a significant number of Buddhist scriptures, sutras, commentaries, and treatises. These texts covered various schools of Buddhist thought, including Theravada, Mahayana, and Vajrayana.

Philosophical Works: The library contained works by both Indian and foreign philosophers, encompassing diverse philosophical traditions such as Nyaya, Vaisheshika, Samkhya, Yoga, Vedanta, and Jain philosophy.

Scientific and Technical Texts: Nalanda's library was not just limited to religious and philosophical texts. It also housed works on mathematics, astronomy, medicine, alchemy, and other scientific disciplines. These texts often represented cutting-edge knowledge of the time.

Literary and Linguistic Works: The library likely had a collection of literary texts, including poetry, drama, and prose, from various languages and cultures. It would have also contained grammatical treatises and linguistic studies.

Historical and Political Treatises: Given its importance as a center of learning and its role in the political landscape of ancient India, Nalanda's library likely had texts related to history, politics, governance, and law.

Art and Aesthetics: The library may have also contained texts on art, architecture, music, and aesthetics, reflecting the cultural and artistic interests of the time.

The exact contents of the library's collection are not fully known, as much of it was lost during the destruction of Nalanda University. However, historical accounts and archaeological findings suggest that the library was incredibly rich and diverse, making it one of the most renowned centers of learning in the ancient world.

The users of the Nalanda University Library were primarily scholars, Monks and Religious Practitioners, and students who came from various parts of Asia to study and conduct research. These individuals were drawn to Nalanda because of its reputation as a premier center of learning, particularly in Buddhist studies and other fields of knowledge.

Development of Collections

A copper plate found when the monastery's ruins were being excavated showed the grant's date of Bengal's Pala emperor Devapala ruled over a few villages for the writing of religious texts such as the Dharmaratna (a religious book) in addition to other messages. It's interesting to observe that routine copying the copyists created the manuscripts, and they were utilized in the Monastery in this capacity. The costs were confirmed by the people who needed the copies. Additionally, among these skilled replicators, there were other pious individuals those who took up the task of replicating the holy books as a part of their obligation. The students also must have made their own copies for their self-study. It is said that several thousands of monks lived in this Monastery, and they devoted themselves in the task of copying the religious texts which must have made numerous and frequent additions to the library. When a Buddhist scholar at Nalanda died, his manuscripts were added to the library collection.

(Prajnaparamita and Scenes from the Buddha's Life (top), Maitreya and Scenes from the Buddha's Life (bottom), Folios from a Dharmasamgraha, manuscript from Nalanda, circa 1075)

(Avalokiteshvara Bodhisattva. *Ashtasahasrika Prajnyaparamita Sutra* manuscript from Nalanda's Pala period.)

Destruction of the library

The destruction of the Nalanda Library and the university itself is a significant event in history, marking the decline of one of the world's oldest and most renowned centers of learning. The exact details of its destruction are not entirely clear, but historical accounts suggest that it occurred during the 12th century CE, during the period of Turkic invasions in India.

In some texts it is mentioned that the Nalanda University was destroyed thrice by attackers, but reconstructed only two times. The first destruction was done by the Hunas under Mihirakula during the rule of Skandagupta (455-467 AD). But successors of Skandagupta rebuilt the library and developed it with an even larger building. The second destruction was caused by the Gaudas in the early seventh century and after sometime the Buddhist Emperor Harshavardhana (606-648 AD) reconstructed the university. The third and heavy damaging attack came while the old Nalanda University, world famous centre of Buddhist knowledge, was destroyed by the Turkish Muslim invader Bakhtiyar Khilji in 1193. This unfortunate milestone event was the main cause behind the decline of Buddhism in India. It was a main centre of knowledge and study from the fifth century CE to 1200 CE and now included in the "World Heritage Site of the Unesco".

It is believed that Bakhtiyar Khilji had suffered from illness and doctors in his darbar were not able to treat him. Then, someone opined him to go to Rahul Sri Bhadra, the chief of Nalanda University for treatment. Khilji was very proud on his religious culture and denied to go for a treatment by an individual other than his Islamic religion. But his health badly declined and he had no other option but to call Bhadra from Nalanda University. He set a condition and asked Bhadra to treat him with no medicines. Bhadra then replied Khilji to read some pages of the Quran as a cure for his sickness after that Khilji start reading the Quran, Eventually, the Khilji was cured of the disease and miracle was occurring. Khilji was Upset by the experience that a Hindu doctor and scholar had more knowledge than the doctors of his darbar, Khilji determined to sabotage the soul of knowledge of ayurveda and Buddhism from the Indian soil. He burned the huge library of Nalanda and destroyed about nine million manuscripts. His target during the attack is the library, with its vast collection of manuscripts and texts, it is believed that the library's priceless manuscripts were destroyed in the fires that engulfed the university, resulting in the loss of centuries' worth of knowledge.

It is said that the library was so broad and strong that it consumed three months to destroy it completely. The Turkish attackers also killed Buddhist scholars and monks in the Nalanda University. It is generally accepted that Buddhism as a main religion in India faced a trouble for centuries due to the destruction of the religious literature during the attacks. The destruction of Nalanda University had a profound impact on learning in the region. It marked the end of an era of intellectual flourishing and the dispersal of scholars and students who had been associated with the university.

Fleeing monks took some of the Nalanda manuscripts. A few of them have survived and are preserved in collections such as those at:

Asia Society: This Ashtasahasrika Prajnaparamita manuscript records, in Sanskrit and Tibetan, the history of the manuscript from its creation at the famous Nalanda monastery in India through its use in Tibet by the compiler of the first Tibetan canon of Buddhism, Buton.

Yarlung Museum, Tsetang: Astasahasrika Prajnaparamita Sanskrit palm-leaf manuscript, with 139 leaves and painted wooden covers. According to the colophon, this manuscript was donated by the mother of the great pandita Sri Asoka in the second year of the reign of King Surapala at end of the 11th century.

and since then, the University has not been restored till the current development. The newly constructed campus spread over 455 acres in Rajgir city of Bihar, Nalanda University began its academic session on 1 September 2014 with 15 scholars from all over the world.

Conclusion

The historical legacy of Nalanda, once a beacon of learning and intellectual exchange, is a testament to the heights of knowledge achieved in ancient India. Its vast library, Dharmaganja, held an unparalleled collection of texts across multiple disciplines, serving as a major center for Buddhist learning as well as science, medicine, philosophy, and more. The destruction of Nalanda, particularly by Bakhtiyar Khilji in the late 12th century, marked a significant loss for global knowledge and Buddhist scholarship. Despite its tragic end, the rediscovery and excavation of Nalanda have rekindled interest in its contributions to education and culture. Efforts to revive the spirit of Nalanda culminated in the establishment of the modern Nalanda University, reflecting a commitment to restore its reputation as a center for international learning. Nalanda's destruction serves as a poignant reminder of the fragility of knowledge, but its legacy continues to inspire new generations of scholars and learners worldwide. The re-establishment of Nalanda University in 2014 represents a symbolic rebirth of this ancient institution, aiming to reclaim its stature as a global center of education and research. Nalanda's enduring legacy reminds us of the fragility of knowledge and the importance of its preservation for future generations.

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